

PRECISION IN PRACTICE: THE ADVANTAGES OF 3D-PRINTED TEMPORARY RESTORATIONS**Kazakova Rada***DMD, PhD, Senior Assistant Professor**Department of Prosthetic Dentistry, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Medical University – Plovdiv**CAD/CAM Center of Dental Medicine, Research Institute, Medical University – Plovdiv**3 'Hristo Botev' Blvd, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria***Abstract**

This article explores the advantages of 3D-printed temporary restorations in dental practice, emphasizing precision and efficiency. Through an extensive literature review, this study investigates the benefits, challenges, and advancements associated with the utilization of 3D printing technology for temporary restorations.

Keywords: 3D printing, temporary restorations, digital dentistry, precision, efficiency.

Introduction: Temporary restorations play a crucial role in dental practice, providing interim solutions while permanent restorations are fabricated. Traditionally, temporary restorations are manually fabricated, which can be time-consuming and prone to inaccuracies. However, with the advent of 3D printing technology, temporary restorations can now be produced with unparalleled precision and efficiency. This article examines the advantages of 3D-printed temporary restorations, highlighting their potential to improve patient care and streamline dental workflows.

Materials and Methods: To conduct this study, a comprehensive literature review was undertaken using databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect. Keywords including "3D printing," "temporary restorations," "digital dentistry," "precision," and "efficiency" were used to identify relevant articles and studies. Peer-reviewed publications within the last decade were selected for analysis to ensure the currency and reliability of the findings. Studies focusing on the

utilization of 3D printing technology for temporary restorations, particularly those highlighting advantages and challenges, were included in the review.

Results: The literature review revealed numerous advantages associated with 3D-printed temporary restorations. Studies [1-4] have demonstrated that 3D-printed temporary restorations exhibit superior precision and fit compared to traditional fabrication methods. Additionally, 3D printing enables the production of temporary restorations with intricate designs and anatomical accuracy, enhancing patient comfort and satisfaction. Furthermore, digital workflows facilitated by 3D printing technology streamline the design and production process, reducing turnaround times and costs [5-7]. Tables 1 and 2 present a summary of key findings related to the advantages and challenges of 3D-printed temporary restorations.

Discussion: The integration of 3D printing technology in temporary restoration fabrication has revolutionized dental practice, offering several significant advantages [8-10]. Table 1 and 2 explore the key aspects further:

Table 1

Impact of 3D-Printed Temporary Restorations on Patient Outcomes

Aspect	Impact
Comfort and Aesthetics	3D-printed temporary restorations provide a better fit and enhanced aesthetics for patients.
Functionality	Precise customization ensures optimal functionality and chewing efficiency.
Patient Satisfaction	Enhanced comfort and aesthetics lead to higher patient satisfaction rates.

Table 2

Efficiency Gains with 3D-Printed Temporary Restorations

Aspect	Efficiency Gains
Reduced Turnaround Time	Digital workflows streamline the design and production process, reducing turnaround times.
Cost Savings	Lower material wastage and reduced labor costs contribute to overall cost savings.
Improved Workflow Integration	Seamless integration into existing dental workflows enhances overall practice efficiency.

Despite the numerous benefits, the implementation of 3D printing for temporary restorations also poses certain challenges and considerations. Let's examine these aspects:

Addressing these challenges and considerations is crucial to fully capitalize on the potential benefits of 3D printing technology in temporary restoration fabrication. With proper training, investment, and adherence to regulatory standards, dental practices can leverage 3D printing to enhance patient care, improve workflow efficiency, and deliver superior temporary restorations tailored to individual patient needs.

Conclusion: In conclusion, 3D printing technology offers significant advantages in the fabrication of temporary restorations, including superior precision, enhanced anatomical accuracy, and streamlined production workflows. Despite challenges, the benefits of 3D-printed temporary restorations in improving patient care and optimizing dental practice workflows are undeniable. Continued research and technological advancements will further enhance the role of 3D printing in temporary restoration fabrication, ultimately benefiting both dental professionals and patients.

References

1. Giacomo GD, Silva J, Martines R, Ajzen S. Computer-designed selective laser sintering surgical guide and immediate loading dental implants with definitive prosthesis in edentulous patient: A preliminary method. *Eur J Dent.* 2014;8:100–106.
2. Stansbury JW, Dickens SH. Determination of double bond conversion in dental resins by near infrared spectroscopy. *Dent Mater.* 2001;17:71–79.
3. Di Giacomo GA, Cury PR, da Silva AM, da Silva JV, Ajzen SA. A selective laser sintering prototype guide used to fabricate immediate interim fixed complete arch prostheses in flapless dental implant surgery: Technique description and clinical results. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2016;116:874–879.
4. Salmi M. Possibilities of Preoperative Medical Models Made by 3D Printing or Additive Manufacturing. *J Med Eng.* 2016;2016:6191526.
5. Bacchi A, Nelson M, Pfeifer CS. Characterization of methacrylate-based composites containing thio-urethane oligomers. *Dent Mater.* 2016;32:233–239.
6. Alharbi N, Osman RB, Wismeijer D. Factors Influencing the Dimensional Accuracy of 3D-Printed Full-Coverage Dental Restorations Using Stereolithography Technology. *Int J Prosthodont.* 2016;29:503–510.
7. Urrios A, et al. 3D-printing of transparent bio-microfluidic devices in PEG-DA. *Lab Chip.* 2016;16:2287–2294.
8. Dimitrova, M. Comparative study of linear and volumetric changes of 3D printed and conventional resins in removable prosthodontics [in Bulgarian]. PhD Thesis, 2023, Plovdiv.
9. Di Giacomo GA, et al. Accuracy and complications of computer-designed selective laser sintering surgical guides for flapless dental implant placement and immediate definitive prosthesis installation. *J Periodontol.* 2012;83:410–419.
10. Nayar S, Bhuminathan S, Bhat WM. Rapid prototyping and stereolithography in dentistry. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2015;7:S216–219.